

The Conventional System of Zakah versus the Holy Quran: An Econometric Model of Payers and Receivers

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Abstract

Zakah is the socio-economic obligatory act of worship most often mentioned in the Holy Qur'an along with *Salat* (prayer). The rules given by Almighty Allah, especially regarding the obligatory acts, are changed from the beginning by the plot of *Satan* (Devil). So many Prophets and Messengers came and the Prophet of the Holy Quran confirmed this is the only principle to guide our lives. This article examines whether Muslim countries have Zakah management according to the principles and regulations mentioned in the Holy Quran. To achieve this objective, contemporary data and information from forty Muslim-majority countries were collected and analyzed. A thorough review revealed that the conventional system of Zakah has a *Nisab* (minimum amount) and a rate of 2.5%. These two basic elements, the existence of which is not mentioned anywhere in the Holy Quran. Moreover, it appears that all forms of management of Zakah have been developed purely on economic considerations, that is the social aspect has been completely rejected. It is also seen that some countries collect this Zakah officially and it is spent in non-authorized ways of the Holy Quran. Furthermore, even though sectarian conflicts in the present Muslim world have been involved in destructive ways such as war, followers of one school of thought regarding Zakah. It is mentioned that although the principle of harvest and *Khumus* (one-fifth) of the Holy Quran identifies the Zakah receiving class, in reality, there is no system of such distribution among those classes either by Zakah or otherwise. This argues a review of the rules of Zakah compiled between the 11th and 18th centuries because the Zakah system was based on the same principle from Abraham to the Prophet of the Holy Quran.

Keywords: Holy Quran; Zakah; Nisab; Rate of Zakah; Zakah Payer and Receiver; Socio-Economic

1. Introduction

We see some of the socio-economic variables in the Holy Quran include *Infaq* (spending in general), *Sadaqa* (giving willingly), *Anfal* (mineral wealth that the state will distribute), and *Zakah* (to attain purity). The only scripture of the principles of Islam is the Holy Quran where are the rules and principles of *Infaq*, *Sadaqah*, *Zakah*, and *Anfal* in various verses. The word *Khums* (one-fifth) is used in the Holy Quran where it is said, "Surely a fifth of it is for Allah and for the Messenger, the near relatives, the orphans, the poor and the traveler if you believe (Q: 8:41)." Nowadays, Majority of Islamic countries have stipulated to pay *Zakah* at the rate of 2.5% on 'Nisab' amount that is a certain amount of wealth. However, this 2.5% does not exist anywhere in the Holy Quran. However, this paper is only for *Zakah*, thus, there is no discussion, review, or analysis of *Infaq*, *Sadaqah*, *Anfal*, and *Khums*, so these variables have been avoided intentionally.

The basic purpose of this paper is to create a socio-economic profile of *Zakah* payers and receivers by highlighting the similarities and contrasts between the conventional *Zakah* system and those mentioned in the Holy Quran. In the conventional system, *Zakah* (Arabic: زكاة *Zakah*), "that which purifies", also (Arabic: المال زكاة), "*Zakah* of wealth" is one of the five pillars of Islam (Nasim 2009). Every independent, adult Muslim male and female is entitled to a fixed portion of his/her income and property each year if it exceeds *Nisab* (the limit amount) prescribed by Islamic Shari'ah (Qaradawi 2011), the rule of distribution among the poor and needy is called *Zakah* (Salehi and AriyanPoour 2014; Lessy 2009). Generally, property over the prescribed *Nisab* during the Hijri year then *Zakah* is to be distributed 2.5% percent or 1/40th share of the total assets (Kulayni et al 2015).

We believe that the fundamental scripture for all Muslims regardless of time, and place is the Holy Quran of Almighty Allah. In this Quran, there are written rules regarding every matter for the people. The main holy scriptures are in Arabic, in that case, at least in the case of Arab states, there should be no difference in easily understanding and following the fundamentals of the Holy Quran. Although in most cases there are various sects (Shia, Sunni, Sufi, Mu'tazila, and so on) and schools of Islamic theology on very basic issues. All these schools of Islamic theology have conflicts, resulting in the most deadly and destructive activity in the modern world, war, which continues day after day, month after month, year after year, even for centuries. However, Almighty Allah, in more than a hundred verses of the Holy Quran, has urged people to think and study the Quran in detail. We know that *Zakah* is an obligatory act of worship, but there are many differences between states, especially in terms of collection, calculation, and enforcement of payers and receivers.

Although the basic objectives of this study are discussed in the introduction, the specific objectives are the following three such as to measure the similarities and contrasts between the conventional *Zakah* system and the mentioned in the Holy Quran; to propose an econometric model of socio-economic and demographic profiles of *Zakah* payers and recipients based on the Holy.

2. Literature review

First of all, we can take a look at how and to what extent Allah Almighty has told us about Zakah in the Holy Quran. The word Zakah is directly used in thirty verses of the Holy Quran. Twenty-five of these thirty verses are related to *Salat* (prayer), meaning that the Zakah payer must be a Salat performer. There are almost ninety-five statistical variables in Salat, that is the sum of these variables is Salat (Mannan 2022). Therefore, to fully understand Zakah, one must understand well all the variables connected with Zakah, this is the basic principle of the Holy Quran.

Let's see what are the direct variables connected with Zakah in the Holy Quran. It can be seen all these variables may divided into four categories, firstly, individual beliefs and self-efficacy variables that are believe in Allah, believe the last day, believe the Angels, believe in the scriptures, believe in the Prophets (Q: 2:177); do not worship except Allah (Q: 2:83); patient in poverty, patient in hardship (Q: 2:177); support to the Messengers, loan to Allah a goodly loan (Q: 5:12); fear to Allah (Q: 7:156); repentant (Q: 9:5); do not fear except Allah (Q: 9:18); obey Allah, obey his Messenger (Q: 9:71); worshippers of only for Allah (Q: 21:73); Allah belongs the outcome of matters (Q: 22:41); The religion of your father, Abraham, Muslim, hold fast to Allah, Allah is the best protector (Q: 22:78); fear a Day in which the hearts and eyes will turn about (Q: 24:37); The hereafter they are certain in faith (Q: 27:3); desiring the countenance of Allah (Q: 30:39); The hereafter, are certain in strong faith (Q: 31:4); recite what is easy for you of the Qur'an (Q: 73:20) and worship Allah, being sincere (Q: 98:5).

Secondly, socioeconomic and sociodemographic variables of the payers, category include twenty-one such as establish prayer, bow with those who bow (Q: 2:43); to parents do good, to relatives to good, to orphans, do good, to the needy do good, speak to people well (Q: 2:83); honest job (Q: 2:110); fulfill their promise, be patient during battle, truthfulness (Q: 2:177); restrain hands, jihad (Q: 4:77); give Zakah by bowing (Q: 5:55); the Mosques of Allah to be maintained (Q: 9:18); believers are friends to each other (Q: 9:71); used to enjoin family member's for praying (Q: 19:55); active (Q: 23:4), in the business remembrance of Allah (Q: 24:37); stay at home (Q: 33:33); give Sadaka (Q: 58:13). Thirdly, socioeconomic variables of the recipient are seen only five such as those who give wealth despite their attachment to close relatives, orphans, helpless, travelers, supplicants, and freed slaves (Q: 2:177). Fourthly, payers' other variables, are prohibited activities such as interest (Q: 30:39); abandonment of the decorations of the ancient Jahili era (Q: 33:33); and unbelievers in the hereafter (Q: 41:7). Finally, Allah said a few obey (Q: 2:83).

In the light of the Holy Quran, we can know the complete rules of Zakah with the help of other verses related to the above variables. For example, Allah has not told us where and what amount of Zakah should be given directly in the verse. However, Khums states in principle "One-fifth for the Prophet, close relatives, orphans, the poor and the traveler" (Q: 9:35). We see that this class is the recipient of Zakah. Since no other ratio of distribution has been prescribed for this category in the Holy Qur'an, it is a matter of consideration whether it is reasonable to accept man-made ratios without accepting this provision. The second question is when to give Zakah. The answer to this question is not in the above verses. But "give it its right when it bears fruit and, on the day, it is reaped." (Q: 6: 141). In addition, Allah has said "And in their wealth is the right of the aspirant and the destitute." (Q: 51:19). Moreover, "those who have their wealth have a fixed right

(Q: 70:24). This category is Zakah receivers, but it is clear in the verses of Zakah. Almighty Allah has told us to think and study this Quran several times.

Now we can review how conventional Zakah practices and methods have been taught to us. In this case, the forty predominantly Muslim countries are considered in this study. Those countries were reviewed in three categories. First are countries where Zakah is compulsory and collected by the state, such as Libya, Malaysia, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, Sudan, and Yemen. Each of these countries has statutory laws and regulations regarding Zakah. For example, in the case of Libya, although there is Zakah Law LIBYAN ACT NO: 89, 1971, there is no statutory provision for calculating Zakah (Ministry of Planning of Libya 2021). Malaysia has about fifteen laws, even though they have Sharia law and different provisions for each state, but there are also various complications related to Zakah (Hasbulah et al 2022). Pakistan forms its national budget by collecting Zakah from the people at the rate of 2.5%, which plays a huge role in the socio-economic sector of the country (Toor and Nasar 2004). The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia believes in Fiqh, so even though they change Nisab from time to time depending on their country's economy, they keep the Zakah payment rate unchanged at 2.5% (Sadeq 2002). Collected by Sudan at a rate of 2.5%, they play an important role in providing cash, food, health care, and education services to the poor (Machado et al 2018). The Yemen government has a mandatory 2.5% Zakah system for both individuals and corporate entities, and all are required to pay adequate income tax, but Yemen's Nisab calculation slightly differs from Saudi Arabia (Obaid et al 2020).

There is no government system for collecting Zakah in several countries, but they have some of the rules and regulations for the Zakah practice. For example, Zakah has managed asset distribution and project financing by managing and investing Zakah funds as microcredits to contribute to financing local development and encouraging investment by providing financial support and loans in microfinance, to create jobs, reduce unemployment and poverty in Algeria (Sayah and Musari 2021). Zakah Institutions in Azerbaijan are intermediary organizations that work to help in the Zakah management process by considering the social impact and in this process, recognize a part of Amil as a Zakah recipient and take all of the operating expenses from the collected Zakah and *Infraq* (spending) funds, albeit to a limited extent from many (Lubis et al 2018). Zakah is payable at 2.5% of assets above the Burkina Faso Nisab and the Nisab is 85 grams of 24-carat gold (Shirazi and Amin 2009) and a similar provision is found in Guinea (Gomez 2010) and Chad (Ali and Hatta 2014), but there are differences in the Nisab.

A study from Iraq shows that Zakah plays an important role in poverty alleviation but there is no change in the Nisab and rate of Zakah (Subhan 2018). Soviet rule severely affected conventional Zakah management among other religious practices in Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, and Turkmenistan, from generation to generation (Mahomed 2022; Lessy 2013; Clement 2020). Zakah collection and distribution systems in these countries are largely limited to informal practices, due to the absence of Zakah institutions or state intervention since Soviet rule. African countries such as Mali (Weiss 2020), Mauritania (IMF 2013), Morocco (Lahjouji and Rouggani 2016), Niger (Obaid et al 2020), Nigeria (Ayuba 2016), Senegal (Herzog and Mui 2016), Sierra Leone (Thaler et al 2013), Somalia (Farah and Haji-Othman 2020) and the Gambia (Gassama 2021) have seen predominantly NGO-based Zakah management. All these countries

also show some differences in other customs of Islam, but not much difference is seen in the case of Zakah.

In other countries such as the Middle Eastern country of Oman, Zakah plays an important role in poverty alleviation (Al-Hadhramia et al 2021). Although high-income Islamic countries such as Qatar (Muhammad 2019) and Turkey (Cokrohadisumarto and Zaenudin 2022) should be exemplary models to other Islamic countries, the participation of renowned Islamic scholars to issue opinions and fatwas on Zakah law has included the use of modern technology to promote transparency and compliance. However, no leading role is seen in its implementation. The cases of Syria (Selvik 2013) and Tunisia (Daly and Frikha 2015) show that Zakah supports emergency services within the country, such as sponsoring medical professionals, providing equipment and medicine, and even providing generators, fuel, and other essential items, especially those needed by the healthcare sector. Although there is some variation in how countries determine the Nisab, there is no change in the 2.5% principle for paying Zakah.

The third list of optional countries is Bahrain, Bangladesh, Egypt, Indonesia, Iran, Jordan, Kuwait, Lebanon, and the United Arab Emirates. These studies have revealed that Bahrain (Abdelbaki 2013), Jordan (Machado et al 2018), Kuwait (Mahmood et al 2022), Lebanon (Gazar 2021), and United Arab Emirates (Younus and Ahmad 2021) contribute a lot to the GDP of these countries, but there is a lot of opacity in the distribution management, questioning the principle of Zakah. According to Egypt, the once-a-year Zakah payable to poor families is likely to be much higher in reality, meaning that Zakah management has considerable flaws (Bremer 2013). In Indonesia (Syamsuri et al 2022) it has been observed that the role of Zakah has proven to be an alternative way to reduce poverty for various communities, especially Muslims in Indonesia (Syamsuri et al 2022). Iranian Muslims usually pay their Zakah to the office of the Higher Religious Authority, which is a charity organization approved by the state authorities, although Iran is a Shia state, the Nisab and Zakah rates are almost the same, but some pay Zakah at a rate of 10% (Sardar et al 2019). In the case of Bangladesh, 3.79% and 2.33% contribute respectively to the GDP in classical and contemporary systems (Jahangir and Bulut 2022). There is only one Zakah Fund Ordinance (The Zakah Fund Ordinance, 1982) which provides for the formation of a Zakah Board, but there is no law or policy regarding any Nisab or rates. The people of Bangladesh follow their own *Madhhab* (a school of thought within Islamic jurisprudence), *Pir* (a Muslim saint or holy man), and *Mashayek* (Sufis, mystics, holy persons, dervishes) rules.

Of the forty Muslim-majority countries in the world, Zakah is compulsory and collected by the state in six countries: Libya, Malaysia, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, Sudan, and Yemen. There is no government system for Zakah collection in Afghanistan, Algeria, Azerbaijan, Burkina Faso, Chad, Guinea, Iraq, Kazakhstan, Mali, Mauritania, Morocco, Niger, Nigeria, Oman, Qatar, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Somalia, Syria, Tajikistan, Gambia, Tunisia, Turkey, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan. Countries that are optional for people are Bahrain, Bangladesh, Egypt, Indonesia, Iran, Jordan, Kuwait, Lebanon, and the United Arab Emirates. Despite being a fully Islamic country and even a Muslim-majority country, Zakah varies greatly from country to country and this disparity is the main motivation for this research paper.

Although there is disagreement among the madhhabs of these forty countries, there is no disagreement on the determination of Nisab and the 2.5% rate of Zakah. It has already been mentioned that the Holy Qur'an does not have this type of calculation except for one-fifth. Even this type of Nisab determination is not mentioned anywhere in the Holy Quran. That is, this Nisab and 2.5% came from the fatwa that is mentioned in Al-Hidaya, vol.1, pages 185-195, which is the regulation of Zakah for the modern Muslim world (Mesbah 2007). Al-Hidaya is one of the Hanafi jurisprudences. This book was written by Imam Burhan Uddin Abul Hasan Ali Abu Bakr. He was born in Marginan, Afghanistan, and lived in (1117-1179) AD with Hijri year (511-593) (Mesbah 2007).

In this literature review, it has been realized that mainly the Nisab and 2.5% were established. Although the law of Zakah is from Ibrahim and later other prophets and messengers, even the last Prophet has confirmed it. In addition to Al-Hidaya, such rulings are found in Fatwa'i Shami, Badayus Sana'i, Sunan Abu Dawud, Sunan Kubra Bayhaqi, Mu'atta Imam Malek, Musannaf Abdur Razaq, Musannaf Ibn Abi Shayba, Albahrur Rayek and many such books. But Almighty Allah has told us in the Holy Qur'an, "This is the law of Allah, which has come from before; you will not find any change in this law of Allah." (Q: 48:23)

3. Research Methodology

Two methods have been adopted in this study. First is the formulation of a socio-economic theoretical model by analyzing the verses directly referring to Zakah mentioned in the Holy Qur'an. Second, based on recent studies on Zakah from forty majority Muslim countries, data will be presented and analyzed in comparison with conventional methods and the Holy Qur'an.

3.1 Theoretical model

In this study, thirty verses of the Holy Quran directly mention Zakah, therefore, only those verses are considered. Although some consider thirty-two and others thirty-four as Zakah verses. Those verses mainly considered to be related to *Infaq* (spending) and *Sadaqah* (a voluntary charitable act), have been excluded from this study. The verses were identified through analysis as fifty-eight variables, which are detailed in Appendix (A-D). All the variables were further divided into five categories such as individual belief and self-development (twenty-seven items); Socio-economic and demographic status of the donor (twenty-one), socio-economic status of the recipient (six), related factors of the donor (three) and given by Allah (one). So, to analyze the Zakah payer in a country or at large we can create an econometrics model combining all the variables, (see Equation 1.1)

$$\text{Zak} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{BeInAh} + \alpha_2 \text{BeILD} + \alpha_3 \text{BeAlIs} + \alpha_4 \text{BeKit} + \alpha_5 \text{BePts} + \alpha_6 \text{DnWeA} + \alpha_7 \text{PatPov} + \alpha_8 \text{PatHip} + \alpha_9 \text{SupMgs} + \alpha_{10} \text{LAaGL} + \alpha_{11} \text{FerAlh} + \alpha_{12} \text{Rept} + \alpha_{13} \text{DnFeAlh} + \alpha_{14} \text{ObeAlh} + \alpha_{15} \text{ObeMes} + \alpha_{16} \text{WOAllh} + \alpha_{17} \text{AlhOM} + \alpha_{18} \text{ReFAB} + \alpha_{19} \text{Musl} + \alpha_{20} \text{HFAlh} + \alpha_{21} \text{AlhbP} + \alpha_{22} \text{FeHETa} + \alpha_{23} \text{HCiFth} + \alpha_{24} \text{DCAlh} + \alpha_{25} \text{HCiSFth} + \alpha_{26} \text{RecHQr} + \alpha_{27} \text{WAlgBS} + \alpha_{28} \text{EstdPer} + \alpha_{29} \text{BoWBo} + \alpha_{30} \text{TPrnDG} + \alpha_{31} \text{TReIDG} + \alpha_{32} \text{TOrpDG} + \alpha_{33} \text{TNedDG} + \alpha_{34} \text{SpkPG} + \alpha_{35} \text{HnsJb} + \alpha_{36} \text{FulPr} + \alpha_{37} \text{BPatDB} + \alpha_{38} \text{TrFlns} + \alpha_{39} \text{ResHns} + \alpha_{40} \text{Jhd} + \alpha_{41} \text{GZakBB} + \alpha_{42} \text{MsqAlhM} + \alpha_{43} \text{BeFEO} + \alpha_{44} \text{UsEnFMP} + \alpha_{45} \text{Actv} + \alpha_{46} \text{BusReAlh} + \alpha_{47} \text{StyAH} + \alpha_{48} \text{GivSdka} + \alpha_{49} \text{RiBa} + \alpha_{50} \text{ADAJer} + \alpha_{51} \text{UnbHA} + e_1 \dots\dots\dots \text{(Equation 1.1)}$$

Here e_1 is the deviation (error term)

Equation 1.1 above, can analyze the Zakah giver with twenty-seven variables of individual faith and self-improvement separately. Basically, in the light of the Holy Qur'an, only these people give and will only pay Zakah. These variables are mainly related to the individual's beliefs and psyche, which may not be seen externally but can be considered with related activities. One can code these variables as per the needs of the study. The single-person model is represented by Equation 1.2 below:

$$\text{InChFSI} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{BeInAh} + \beta_2 \text{BeILD} + \beta_3 \text{BeAlS} + \beta_4 \text{BeKit} + \beta_5 \text{BePts} + \beta_6 \text{DnWeA} + \beta_7 \text{PatPov} + \beta_8 \text{PatHip} + \beta_9 \text{SupMgs} + \beta_{10} \text{LAaGL} + \beta_{11} \text{FerAlh} + \beta_{12} \text{Rept} + \beta_{13} \text{DnFeAlh} + \beta_{14} \text{ObeAlh} + \beta_{15} \text{ObeMes} + \beta_{16} \text{WOAllh} + \beta_{17} \text{AlhOM} + \beta_{18} \text{ReFAB} + \beta_{19} \text{Musl} + \beta_{20} \text{HFAlh} + \beta_{21} \text{Alhbp} + \beta_{22} \text{FeHETa} + \beta_{23} \text{HCiFth} + \beta_{24} \text{DCAlh} + \beta_{25} \text{HCiSFth} + \beta_{26} \text{RechQR} + \beta_{27} \text{WAlgBS} + e_1 \dots\dots\dots$$

(Equation 1.2)

Here e_1 is the deviation (error term)

Twenty-one variables have been highlighted considering the socio-economic and demographic status of the payer. That is, the Zakah payer is somehow connected with the society. A scholarship can collect information about Zakah payers through observation or his/her chosen process for his/her study and coding in his/her convenient way. This model is represented below by Equation 1.3.

$$\text{SOciPP} = \mu_0 + \mu_1 \text{EstdPer} + \mu_2 \text{BoWBo} + \mu_3 \text{TPrnDG} + \mu_4 \text{TReIDG} + \mu_5 \text{TOrpDG} + \mu_6 \text{TNedDG} + \mu_7 \text{SpkPG} + \mu_8 \text{HnsJb} + \mu_9 \text{FulPr} + \mu_{10} \text{BPatDB} + \mu_{11} \text{TrFlns} + \mu_{12} \text{ResHns} + \mu_{13} \text{Jhd} + \mu_{14} \text{GZakBB} + \mu_{15} \text{MsqAlhM} + \mu_{16} \text{BeFEO} + \mu_{17} \text{UsEnFMP} + \mu_{18} \text{Actv} + \mu_{19} \text{BusReAlh} + \mu_{20} \text{StyAH} + \mu_{21} \text{GivSdka} + e_1 \dots\dots\dots$$

(Equation 1.3)

Here e_1 is the deviation (error term)

The socio-economic status of the recipient has been informed by Almighty Allah. He mentioned all the moral and social variables in the case of Zakah payers. However, the recipient of the Zakah is not directly mentioned. Therefore, in this study, the model is derived only from the verses that directly refer to Zakah, which is given below as Equation 1.4.

$$\text{SociSR} = \pi_0 + \pi_1 \text{GWislTR} + \pi_2 \text{GWislTO} + \pi_3 \text{GWislTN} + \pi_4 \text{GWislTT} + \pi_5 \text{GWislTA} + \pi_6 \text{GWisIFF} \dots\dots\dots$$

(Equation 1.4)

Here e_1 is the deviation (error term)

Three independent variables related to the donor are included in Equation 1.1 in the basic model of Zakah payer. However, when one variable related to God's information is included in Equation 1.1, no new model is presented in this study.

3.2 Implementation model

In the data analysis and review of this study, ten contemporary published research articles from each of the forty majority Muslim countries were first identified. After initial evaluation, five research papers from each country were re-evaluated for in-depth review. Finally, all the information and data collected from forty study papers from a total of forty countries, one for each country, are presented in Tables 1.4-1.7 below. It is to be noted that the list of study papers used in the final review is provided in Tables 1.1-1.3 below.

Among the forty countries, it can be seen that Zakah is compulsory and collected by the state in six countries as shown in Table 1.1. In addition to the study paper of these six countries, the information in Tables 1.4-1.7 is added and coordinated by reviewing the existing laws and regulations related to Zakah of the countries.

Table 1.1: Zakah is compulsory and collected by the state

Countries	Literature
Libya	Ministry of Planning of Libya (2021)
Malaysia	Hasbulah et al (2022)
Pakistan	Toor & Nasar (2004)
Kingdom of Saudi Arabia	Sadeq (2002)
Sudan	Machado et al. (2018)
Yemen	Obaid et al. (2020)

In the case of twenty-five countries shown in Table 1.2, it can be seen that Zakah is largely compulsory, but there is no state institution to collect it. Zakah payers can pay their Zakah through several institutions or pay them personally.

Table 1.2: There is no government system for Zakah collection

Countries	Literature
Afghanistan	IMF (2008)
Algeria	Sayah & Musari (2021)
Azerbaijan	Lubis et al. (2018)
Burkina Faso	Shirazi & Amin (2009)
Chad	Ali & Hatta (2014)
Guinea	Gómez (2010)
Iraq	Subhan (2018)
Kazakhstan	Mahomed (2020)
Mali	Weiss (2020)
Mauritania	IMF (2013)
Morocco	Lahjouji & Rouggani (2016)
Niger	Obaidullah (2017)
Nigeria	Ayuba (2016)
Oman	Al-Hadhramia et al (2021)
Qatar	Muhammad (2019)
Senegal	Luce (2016)
Sierra Leone	Thaler et al (2013)
Somalia	Farah & Haji-Othman (2020)
Syria	Selvik (2013)
Tajikistan	Lessy (2013)
Gambia	Gassama (2012)
Tunisia	Daly & Frikha (2021)
Türkiye	Cokrohadisumarto & Zaenudin (2022)
Turkmenistan	Clement (2020)
Uzbekistan	Oybekovich et al (2017)

Table 1.3 below lists a total of nine states where Zakah is completely optional for all countries, although there are some Arab states. That is, a person can pay his own Zakah, according to his will, to whomever he/she wants. They can pay or not pay if they want, without any accountability to the state.

Table 1.3: Optional for citizens of countries

Countries	Literature
Bahrain	Hisham H. Abdelbaki (2013)
Bangladesh	Jahangir & Bulut (2013)
Egypt	Bremer (2013)
Indonesia	Syamsuri et al (2022)
Iran	Sardar et al (2019)
Jordan	Machado et al (2018)
Kuwait	Mahmood et al (2022)
Lebanon	Sarea (2021)
United Arab Emirates	Younus & Ahmad (2021)

The above three categories of countries are countries where Zakah is compulsory and collected by the state, countries where there is no government system for Zakah collection, and countries where it is optional for the people. A general picture of this study is presented for analysis and review through Tables 1.4-1.7.

4. Data Analysis

Table 1.4 sets out the minimum amount of Zakah (Nisab) concerning various cash, gold, silver, agricultural, and mineral assets and the rules for Paying Zakah on them. It can be seen that category "A" includes cash, bank deposits, and trading goods with a Nisab value of 612.36 grams. In the current market of Bangladesh, 22-carat silver is fetching about BDT1500 (11.7 per) which is 612.36 grams of silver is BDT78,750. According to this calculation, if a person has more than BDT 78,750 in cash, bank deposits, and business goods in a year, he/she has to pay Zakah at the rate of 2.5% on the total value in that year. It can be said that if BDT 100,000 taka is in the bank, there will be a Zakah of BDT 2500.

Table 1.4: 'Nisab Amount' of Zakah in respect of various cash, gold and silver, agricultural and mineral commodities

Categories	Assets	Nisab (minimum amount)	Rate of Zakah
A.	Cash, bank deposits and trading products	612.36 grams worth of silver	2.5% of full price
B.	Gold, silver or gold-silver ornaments	Gold 87.48 grams and silver 612.36 grams	2.5% of full price
C.	Shares, bank notes, stocks	612.36 grams worth of silver	2.5% of the full price, however, if the company gives Zakah, it is not necessary to pay Zakah personally
D.	Partnerships and <i>Mudaraba</i> (investment)	612.36 grams worth of silver	Zakah should be paid first on property, not on capital; Profits will then be distributed. Zakah will be on personal profits, one share (2.5%) will be paid by the capital provider and one share (2.5%) will be paid by the labor donor.
E.	Agricultural products	According to Abu Hanifa, any amount; According to the Islamic Ecological Research Bureau, 1568 kg	Rain products 10%

F.	Minerals	Any amount	20% on products
G.	Horse	There are three views in this regard	There is no Zakah or 2.5% of a full price or 1 dinar for each horse

Class "B" includes only gold, silver, or gold-silver ornaments where the Nisab is 87.48 grams of gold and 612.36 grams of silver, the rate of Zakah remains unchanged which is 2.5%. The price of silver in Bangladesh in the year 2022 is mentioned earlier and 22-carat gold was BDT 78,000 (11.7 per) which is 87.48 grams about BDT5,85,000. Class "C" includes shares, banknotes, and stocks whose Nisab and rates are similar to class "A", but in this case, the provision is that if the company/business organization pays Zakah, then the individual does not have to pay. Class "D" is partnership business and *Mudaraba* (investment), in that case, the Nisab and rate are unchanged, but the rule is that Zakah must be paid first on the property, not on the capital, and profits will then be distributed. Zakah will be on personal profits, and one share (2.5%) will be paid by the capital provider.

Category "E" includes agricultural products, there are variations in Nisab from Islamic school to school. According to the Hanafi school, any amount but the Islamic Ecological Research Bureau, 1568 kg. However, the rate of Zakah for this category is 10% for rainfed produce. Category "F" includes all types of mineral products, the Nisab of which is any amount and the rate of Zakah is 20% of the product. The "G" category is a horse, the provision of the horse is completely different from other domesticated animals, and even multiple provisions are seen. There are three notable doctrines some say no Zakah, some say 2.5% of the full value, and the third doctrine is 1 dinar for each horse.

Table 1.5 shows the 'Nisab amount' and payable rates of Zakah for sheep and goats. According to this classification, those who have less than forty sheep or goats do not have to pay any Zakah. From forty to two hundred there will be only two if there are two hundred and more then for every eighty have to pay one. In the case of 201-400, it is seen that although there were 2 for 200 for the next 200 it is 1 that is if there are 400 sheep or goats then only 3 Zakah will be given. Whatever the number after 499, for every 100, Zakah will be 1, that is if there are 1000 sheep or goats, Zakah will be 10.

Table 1.5: 'Nisab Amount' of Zakah with respect to sheep and goats

Nisab (minimum amount)	Rate of Zakah
40-120	1 sheep or goat
121-200	2 sheep or goats
201-400	3 sheep or goats
400-499	4 sheep or goats
500 or more	5 sheep or 1 per hundred

Table 1.6 below gives the 'Nisab Amount' and its rate of Zakah concerning cows and buffaloes. In the case of cows and buffaloes, the prevailing rule is that if it is less than 30, he/she does not have to pay Zakah. In the case of Nisab, the first level is taken as 10 in number and the rate is determined by age. A one-year-old calf should be provided for the first 10, followed by a three-year-old calf. If the maximum is more than 100 in that case it will be a two-year-old calf instead of one or three years.

Table 1.6: 'Nisab Amount' of Zakah on Cows and Buffaloes

Nisab (minimum amount)	Rate of Zakah
30-39	1 one year old calf
40-49	1 two-year-old calf
50-59	2 two-year-old calves
60-69	1 three-year-old and 1 two-year-old calf
70-79	2 three-year-old calves
80-89	3 two-year-old calves
90-99	1 three-year-old and 2 two-year-old calves
100-119	A two-year-old calf will be counted as above

Table 1.7 shows the method of determining the 'Nisab amount' and rate of Zakah for camels. If there are less than 5 camels then no Zakah is payable. In determining the rate of Zakah, Golid, goats, and female camels have been given age quotas by determining gender in this way. In the Nisab, three levels are the first level has five camels and one one-year-old goat. It is mentioned that first of all 1 one year old goat is equal to three years old goat. If the number of camels reaches the quota of 25 which is between 25-35 then 4 one-year-old female camels. Thus, if the number of

camels increases, the number of camels in Zakah payment decreases, but their age increases. For example, for 61-75, 1 five-year-old female camel should be given. Thus 150 and above 3 four-year-old female camels and 1 goat for every 5 should be provided.

Table 1.7: 'Nisab Amount' of Zakah to Camels

Nisab (minimum amount)	Rate of Zakah
5-9	1 three-year-old goat or 1 one-year-old goat
10-14	2 one year old goats
15-19	3 one year old goats
20-24	4 one year old goats
25-35	4 one year old female camels
36-45	2 three-year-old female camels
46-60	2 four-year-old female camels
61-75	1 five-year-old female camel
79-90	2 three-year-old female camels
91-120	2 four-year-old female camels
121-129	2 four-year-old female camels and 1 goat
130-134	2 four-year-old female camels and 2 goats
135-139	2 four-year-old female camels and 3 goats
140-144	2 four-year-old female camels and 4 goats
145-149	2 four-year-old female camels and 1 two-year-old camel
150 and above	3 four-year-old female camels and 1 goat in every 5

All of the forty countries represented in this study, as mentioned in Tables 1.4-1.7 above, have set the Nisab and rate of Zakah almost identically. An analysis of the studies and prevailing laws showed that cash, bank deposits, merchandise, gold, silver or gold-silver ornaments, shares, bank notes, stocks, partnership business, *Mudaraba* (investment), agricultural products, minerals, horses, sheep or goats, cows, buffaloes, and camels are divided into fifteen basic sectors of Zakah.

5. Discussion

Most of the studies are in economics or socio-economic context, which was also seen through the data analysis above but in the light of the Holy Qur'an is insufficient. The fifteen basic sectors identified above, the Nisab determining the rate of Zakah, are comparable to wealth tax in various countries, even in Bangladesh. But the principle of the Holy Qur'an is to "give it its right when it bears fruit and, on the day, it is reaped." (Q: 6:141). It is clearly understood that if a land is harvested three times, this right is created three times and by paying it, the rest of the wealth is sanctified. This is Zakah. So, it needs to rethink the principle of applicability of this basis in all cases annually.

Nisab has been determined in categories A-D with the value of gold and silver respectively as cash, bank deposits and trading goods, gold, silver or gold-silver ornaments, shares, bank notes, stocks, partnership business, and *Mudaraba* (investment), and the rate payable is 2.5% on the total value that is capital is not deducted. The existence of this 2.5% is not mentioned anywhere in the Holy Quran. On the other hand, the principle of *Khums* (one-fifth) is mentioned by Allah on dividends. That is, this principle of 2.5% is man-made and all these works are not supportable in the civil and criminal evidence law of the Holy Quran. Perhaps, it is for these reasons that differences of opinion are seen when it comes to agricultural products and horses.

Moreover, *Anfal* (mineral resources) are considered as state property of all countries. Although in this case one-fifth that is 20% is mentioned. In terms of practical application, such as Bangladesh's gas, Indonesia's coal, oil, and gold of Arab countries, everything has been taken by the state as state property. Although *Anfal* (mineral wealth) is not covered by Zakah, Almighty Allah has informed us of a different principle in this regard in the Holy Qur'an. Since this study is not related to this, it could not be discussed in detail.

The way it has fixed the amount of Nisab and provided Zakah in respect of sheep and goats, cows and buffaloes and camels, is completely contrary to the principles of Zakah in the Holy Qur'an. All these principles are determined by people through their own doctrines and religious beliefs. Almighty Allah has not mentioned anywhere that the Zakah payer must be wealthy. On the day of the harvest mentioned above, he/she gave us his rights and explained to us, that even in the mango of a tree, rights are made for our kinsmen, orphans, poor travelers, and supplicants. The Nisab are compiled from other human-authored books. Hence there is a considerable discrepancy between the determination of the amount of Nisab and the calculation of Zakah payable in respect of sheep, goats, cows, buffaloes, and camels.

All studies in economics or socio-economic context are both quantitative and qualitative. Economist or a sociologist does numerous studies from their knowledge, experience, and references, and all the results they get, certainly make new contributions to their respective academic fields, but those variables are not taken into account in the case of the Holy Quran. For example, the contribution of Zakah to poverty alleviation is one of the issues. The Holy Quran, however, does not mention the association of Zakah with the relief of the poor. Therefore, whether the result of relieving the poor through Zakah is positive or negative, has nothing to do with the Holy Quran. Among the fifty-eight variables mentioned, there is no poverty alleviation. Some of

those who are asked to pay Zakah may be poor, but not all may be poor. Such as the near relatives, the orphan, the destitute, the wayfarer, the suppliant, and the freeing of captives (slaves) despite their attachment to the wealth that bestows them (Q: 2:177). Only these five categories are called to pay Zakah. There is no mention that they must be poor. Even in the verses of Khums (Q: 8:41). This study finds all these five categories and the additional two variables are Allah and His Messenger. These two additional variables require in-depth study.

In the six Muslim-majority countries where Zakah is compulsory and collected by the state, there is no justification for Zakah. First of all, Allah has not defined any such state authority in any of the verses of Zakah. Second, the individual's belief and self-improvement variables clearly state that Zakah is what a true believer will give of his own free will, only to five categories. If he/she does not provide it himself, he is also a disbeliever in the Hereafter (Q: 41:7). If he/she is a disbeliever in the Hereafter, there is nothing to do or say, because "there is no compulsion in accepting the Deen." (Q: 2:256). One variable among the five categories mentioned in the Holy Quran is the "prayer". Considering this variable, the state may ask for a share, but it must depend on the circumstances and considerations of the Zakah payer. Therefore, Zakah is compulsory and collection by the state is in stark contrast with the principles of Zakah in the Holy Quran.

The Holy Quran is the scripture of the best theory for mankind, so it is not appropriate to limit the review of Zakah only to the verses of Zakah, because these fifty-eight independent variables are not discussed only in this verse. Rather, each has a different combination of variables. For example, the word Salat appears directly in the Holy Qur'an 96 times in 89 verses, and in separate verses, *Tahajjud* (night prayer) in one time, *Ruku-Sajda* (bowing down and going in prostration) in one time, standing in one time, and *Tasbih* (a form of dhikr that involves the glorification of God) in three times, that is a total of 102 times. In the light of the Holy Quran, a person performing Salat can never accept any man-made law regarding Zakah. Because "And He is Allah; there is no deity except Him. To Him is praise in the first and the Hereafter. And His is the decision, and to Him you will be returned." (Q: 28:70). Thus, no doubt, the detailed analysis of other variables is sufficient for the Holy Quran to answer all questions regarding Zakah.

6. Conclusion

The principle of Islam is the Holy Qur'an sent by Almighty Allah, where the most beautiful social system is connected with every activity of human life. The Holy Quran has given us both micro and macro social systems. From the creation of an ideal family to the global social order. Social order is prioritized in every obligatory worship. This study found that the principles of the Holy Quran are largely neglected in the current system of Zakah. Conventional Zakah management has been judged primarily in terms of financial considerations, that is only wealthy individuals and institutions will pay Zakah and only one class of recipients, namely the poor, will pay Zakah. The class of near relatives is completely neglected. However, the principle of harvesting that Almighty Allah mentioned to us, has been completely abolished. The kind of social ties that this principle urged to strengthen between kinship remained out of consideration. Considering the financial aspects, it is seen that Nisab and the rate of Zakah 2.5% provisions have been implemented following some man-made books called Shariat, completely excluding the principle of Khums. This principle did not find any similarity with the principles of the Holy Quran. However, the Holy

Qur'an has given us a clear idea that Zakah was the same in the era of all the Prophets and Messengers from Ibrahim to the last Prophet, particularly striking is that these customary laws began many centuries after the arrival of the last Prophet and most of them originate from the Eurasian region.

The rules of Zakah compiled in the 11th century or, the 18th century, call for fresh scholarship based on the Holy Quran, as the Zakah practice was based on the same principle from Ibrahim to the last Prophet. It is very important to highlight the social aspects of Zakah through a more in-depth study of the verses related to Zakah.

However, although this study presents a common system of Zakah in forty countries, there may be different types of customs among the people of those countries, that is, within their respective communities, which are not covered by this study. Therefore, in the future, conducting research based on communities in these countries will give a clearer idea.

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Appendix: A

Individual beliefs and self-efficacy variables of the Zakah payer

SL	Verse	Variables	Coding
Dependent Variable			
		Individual beliefs and self-efficacy variables of the Zakah payer	InChFSI
Independent Variables			
1.	2:177	Believe in Allah	BeInAh
2.	2:177	Believe the Last Day	BeILD
3.	2:177	Believe the Angels	BeAls
4.	2:177	Believe in the Kitab	BeKit
5.	2:177	Believe in the Prophets	BePts
6.	2:83	Do not worship except Allah	DnWeA
7.	2:177	Patient in Poverty	PatPov
8.	2:177	Patient in Hardship	PatHip
9.	5:12	Support to the Messengers	SupMgs
10.	5:12	Loan to Allah a Goodly Loan	LAaGL
11.	7:156	Fear to Allah	FerAlh
12.	9:5	Repent	Rept
13.	9:18	Do not Fear Except Allah	DnFeAlh
14.	9:71	Obey Allah	ObeAlh
15.	9:71	Obey His Messenger	ObeMes
16.	21:73	Worshippers of only for Allah	WOAllh
17.	22:41	Allah Belongs the Outcome of Matters	AlhOM
18.	22:78	The Religion of your father, Abraham	ReFAb
19.	22:78	Muslim	Musl
20.	22:78	Hold Fast to Allah	HFAh
21.	22:78	Allah is the Best Protector	AlhbP

22.	24:37	Fear a Day in which the hearts and eyes will turn about	FeHETa
23.	27:3	The Hereafter they are Certain in Faith	HCiFth
24.	30:39	Desiring the Countenance of Allah	DCAIh
25.	31:4	The Hereafter, are certain in Strong Faith	HCiSFth
26.	73:20	Recite what is easy for you of the Qur'an	RecHQr
27.	98:5	Worship Allah, being Sincere	WA1gBS

Appendix: B

Socio-economic and Sociodemographic Variables of Zakah payer

SL	Verse	Variables	Coding
Dependent Variable			
Socioeconomic and Sociodemographic Profile of the Payer			SOciPP
Independent Variable			
1.	2:43	Establish Prayer	EstdPer
2.	2:43	Bow with those who Bow	BoWBo
3.	2:83	To Parents Do Good	TPrnDG
4.	2:83	To Relatives Do Good	TReIDG
5.	2:83	To Orphans, Do Good	TOrpDG
6.	2:83	To the Needy Do Good	TNedDG
7.	2:83	Speak to People Good	SpkPG
8.	2:110	Honest Job	HnsJb
9.	2:177	Fulfill their Promise	FulPr
10.	2:177	Be Patient during Battle	BPatDB
11.	2:177	Truthfulness	TrFlns
12.	4:77	Restrain Hands	ResHns
13.	4:77	Jihad	Jhd
14.	5:55	Give Zakah By Bowing	GZakBB
15.	9:18	The Mosques of Allah to be Maintained	MsqAlhM

16.	9:71	Believers are Friends to each other	BeFEO
17.	19:55	Used to Enjoin Family Member's for Praying	UsEnFMP
18.	23:4	Active	Actv
19.	24:37	In the Business Remembrance of Allah	BusReAlh
20.	33:33	Stay at Home	StyAH
21.	58:13	Give Sadaka	GivSdka

Appendix: C

Socio-economic status variables of the Zakah recipient

SL	Verse	Variables	Coding
Dependent Variable			
		Socio-economic status of the recipient	SociSR
Independent Variable			
1.	2:177	to Relatives	GWislTR
2.	2:177	to Orphans	GWislTO
3.	2:177	to the Needy	GWislTN
4.	2:177	to the Traveler	GWislTT
5.	2:177	to those who Ask	GWislTA
6.	2:177	for Freeing Slaves	GWislFFS

Appendix: D

Other variables of the Zakah payer

SL	Verse	Variables in English	Coding
1.	30:39	Riba	RiBa
2.	33:33	Abandoning the Decorations of the Ancient Jahili era	ADAJer
3.	41:7	Unbelievers in the Hereafter	UnbHA

Information given by Allah

1. 2:83 Few Obeyed

FwObd